

Inclusion of 40+ axenic liverwort accessions to the bryophyte culture collection

D1.3

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Information

Table 1 - Document information

Project acronym	BRYOMOLECULES
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Table 2 Document's update

Version	Date	Revised by	Comments
0.1	25/02/2026	Nils Cronberg	Preliminary draft
0.2	26/02/2026	Nils Cronberg	Final draft
1.0	27/02/2026	Nils Cronberg, Claudio Varotto	Final version
	13/05/2026	EC	Changes requested by the PO
1.1	24/05/2026	Nils Cronberg	Text and data table edited.
2.0	27/05/2026	Claudio Varotto, Mattia Malfatti	Final revised version

Acknowledgement and disclaimer

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Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the REA can be held responsible for them.

The BRYOMOLECULES project

Liverworts, an ancient group of land plants, are a rich yet underexploited source of a wide range of biologically active compounds with high potential for the bioeconomy sector as ingredients of cosmetics/cosmeceuticals and pharmaceuticals. However, their slow growth rate in nature and the consequent difficulty in obtaining large amounts of single compounds have, until now, severely hindered the in-depth exploration and exploitation of the full spectrum of activities of liverwort secondary metabolites. Recent breakthroughs in the identification of some of the genes involved in the early steps of liverwort-specific compounds suggest that, in addition to the establishment of improved methods for growth in axenic conditions, reconstruction of liverwort metabolic pathways in heterologous systems is a promising way forth towards the practical exploitation of liverwort biochemical diversity and its industrial scale up.

BRYOMOLECULES will provide actionable knowledge on European bryophyte species and their biosynthetic genes, which can be used to produce sustainable, bio-based cosmetics and pharmaceuticals ingredients for the European market.

To do so, the BRYOMOLECULES project will use a combination of the cultivation of axenic cultures and the production of the active compounds in heterologous systems to define the most suitable production platform(s) for their large-scale production. The project will achieve a very sustainable use of the chemical diversity of wild EU bryophyte species, a largely untapped source of high-added-value natural products, without significant impacts on their biodiversity.

Besides the identification of relevant lead compounds for cosmetics/cosmeceuticals and pharmaceuticals, another major impact of the project will be the production and release according to FAIR principles of a database of metabolites and biosynthetic genes of European bryophyte species that will fuel in the years to come the development of novel bio-based products based on bryophyte-derived lead compounds, according to the concept of EU valorising biodiversity for EU bioeconomy.

Project Consortium Members

<p>FONDAZIONE EDMUND MACH dal 1874</p>	Fondazione Edmund Mach (FEM)
<p>HUB INNOVAZIONE TRENINO</p>	Fondazione HUB Innovazione Trentino (HIT) FEM LTP
<p>UNIVERSITÉ JEAN MONNET SAINT-ÉTIENNE</p>	Université Jean Monnet Saint-Etienne (UJM)
<p>PAT Plant Advanced Technologies</p>	Plant Advanced Technologies Pat Sa (PAT)
<p>Bionos Testing Efficacy</p>	Bionos Biotech SI (BIONOS)
<p>LUNDS UNIVERSITET</p>	Lunds Universitet (LU)
<p>UNIVERSYTET MEDYCZNY W LUBLINIE</p>	Uniwersytet Medyczny w Lublinie (UM)
<p>ESF Your Partner in Science</p>	European Science Foundation (ESF)

Table 3 Consortium members

Summary

As reported in the DoA, about half of the accessions of newly collected liverworts from Task 1.2 (see D1.2) will be used to start axenic cultures from either spores or pieces of plant tissue. The list of successfully established cultures will be delivered and part of these species will be used in Task 1.4 for the optimization of the cultivation protocols.

This report shows the results achieved for at least 40 new accessions of liverworts.

Introduction

The goal for this deliverable was to present at least 40 new accessions of liverworts. Here, we present 50 accessions of axenic liverworts which have been selected for downstream analyses in the BRYOMOLECULES project; eight of these are recent additions (not yet subject of RNA sequencing or chemical profiling). Plant material has been mostly collected from Sweden, as well as from Iceland, Norway, Finland, The Faroe Islands and Italy. All samples were provided by LU. Dried voucher specimens are stored by LU. The list includes collection information, such as sampling place, coordinates, date of sampling, and collector names.

The collection contains a wide range of liverworts, including both thallose species and leafy liverworts. Taxon names are provided according to the current European checklist (Hodgetts et al. 2020).

Material and Methods

Plant material has been mostly collected from Sweden, as well as from Iceland, Norway, Finland, The Faroe Islands and Italy. All samples were provided by LU. Dried voucher specimens are stored by LU. The list in Annex 1 includes collection information, such as sampling place, coordinates, date of sampling, and collector names.

Sterile accessions have been achieved by surface sterilisation of either sporophytes or vegetative plant material with a 0.05% solution of Sodium Dichloroisocyanurate for 1-2 minutes, followed by washing with sterile deionised water. Accessions are maintained on Petri dishes with 1% agar in a medium as described by Rudolph et al. (1988). The medium was 2 times the original formulation with an addition of 12 mg of the fungicide Benomyl per litre to reduce the risk of fungal contamination. The accessions were tested for axenic condition by growing the cultures on medium with 0,5% glucose added, followed by visual inspection for presence of colonies of bacteria or fungi. If needed, samples have been treated to eliminate infections by cyanobacteria using the antibiotic erythromycin. Collections are maintained in a culture room under artificial LED-tube light, 16/8 day/night cycles and a mean temperature of 20° C.

Results and Discussion

The main objective was to initiate cultures from surface-sterilised sporophytes when possible. However, many liverwort species rarely produce sporophytes or do so during a narrow period, which is difficult to time, so a substantial number of cultures were initiated from vegetative tissue, which is more challenging and time-consuming, and burdened with a higher failure rate.

The complete list of the successfully established cultures is provided in Annex I, Table A1. The 50 accessions of liverworts represent 45 unique taxa, thus exceeding the expected outcome of the deliverable. A total of 50 accessions have been established in sterile culture, as some of the taxa have been sterilized from different geographical accessions. The collection contains a wide range of liverworts, including both thallose species and leafy liverworts.

Conclusions

The goal for this deliverable was to present at least 40 new accessions of liverworts.

In this document we present 50 accessions of axenic liverworts which have been selected for downstream analyses in the BRYOMOLECULES project. Of the 45 unique taxa brought in sterile culture, until now 42 have been used for RNA-Seq and 34 have been used for chemical profiling. The collection contains a wide range of liverworts, including both thallose species and leafy liverworts.

The inclusion of new accessions is ongoing, and the collection is gradually expanding with taxa of particular interest.

References:

- Rudolph, H., Kirchoff, M., Gliesmann, S. Sphagnum culture techniques. Proc. Methods in Bryology, Nichinan, 1988:25–34: Hattori Botanical Laboratory
- Hodgetts, N. G., L. Söderström, T. L. Blockeel, et al. “An Annotated Checklist of Bryophytes of Europe, Macaronesia and Cyprus.” Journal of Bryology 42, no. 1 (2020): 1–116. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03736687.2019.1694329>.

Annex I

Successfully established sterile cultures of liverworts

Table A1. List of the liverwort accession for which successful sterile cultures were established in Report Period 1.

Column Headers

- **LU accession #:** Refers to the accession ID in the bryophyte collection maintained at LU, started during the earlier Moss Tech project.
- **Bryomolecules ID:** ID code used by the Bryomolecules project. N/A= accession not (yet) used in downstream analyses due to contamination, poor growth or other problem.
- **Species:** Scientific name according to the European checklist
- **Synonym:** Eventual synonyms, mostly older names still commonly occurring in liverwort floras.
- **Source:** Indicates whether the accessions have been obtained from spore cultures or from sterilized vegetative tissue.
- **RNA seq:** Indicates if the accession has been included in transcriptomics analyses (see D3.1)
- **Chem:** Indicates if the accession has been sent for phytochemical profiling (see D2.2)
- **Partner:** Bryomolecules partner responsible for maintaining/providing stock cultures.
- **Clade:** Order designation according to the European checklist.
- **Family:** Family designation according to the European checklist
- **Country:** Country of collection: SE= Sweden, FR= France, NO= Norway, FI= Finland, IS = Iceland, FO = Faroe Islands.
- **N-coordinate/E-coordinate:** Refers to WGS84 position of sampled material
- **Collector:** Name of collector(s)

LU Accession #	Bryomolecules ID	Species	Synonym	Source	RNA seq	Chem	Partner	Clade	Family	Country	N-coordinate	E-coordinate	Collector
340	BM77	<i>Bazzania trilobata</i>		Veg.	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Lepidoziaceae	SE	56.02495	13.12299	Nils Cronberg/Eliza Hayse
360	BM83	<i>Blepharostoma trichophylla</i>		Spore	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Blepharostomaceae	NO	63.3982312	10.1553794	Fia Bengtsson

370	BM86	<i>Calypogeia integristipulum</i>		Veg.	YES	NO	LU	Jungermaniales	Calypogeiaceae	SE	57.05701	14.73088	Nils Cronberg
337	BM75	<i>Cephalozia indet</i>		Spore	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Cephaloziaceae	SE	56.33629	12.88789	Nils Cronberg
353	BM80	<i>Cephalozia ambigua</i>		Spore	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Cephaloziaceae	SE	56.02457	13.11470	Nils Cronberg
361	BM84	<i>Cephalozia bicuspidata</i>		Spore	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Cephaloziaceae	NO	63.3982312	10.1553794	Fia Bengtsson
362	BM85	<i>Cephalozia bicuspidata</i>		Spore	YES	NO	LU	Jungermaniales	Cephaloziaceae	NO	63.3982312	10.1553794	Fia Bengtsson
259	BM55	<i>Fuscocephaliopsis connivens</i>	<i>Cephalozia connivens</i>	Spore	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Cephaloziaceae	SE	55.70383	13.20247	Nils Cronberg
260	BM56	<i>Fuscocephaliopsis lunulifolia</i>	<i>Cephalozia lunulifolia</i>	Spore	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Cephaloziaceae	SE	55.70383	13.20247	Nils Cronberg
346	BM78	<i>Chiloscyphus polyanthos</i>	<i>C. polyanthos var. polyanthos</i>	Veg.	YES	NO	LU	Jungermaniales	Lophocoleaceae	SE	56.08398	12.66345	Nils Cronberg
325	BM71	<i>Crossocalyx hellerianus</i>	<i>Anastrophyllum hellerianum</i>	Veg.	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Anastrophyllaceae	SE	57.10777	14.55772	Nils Cronberg
250	BM54	<i>Diplophyllum albicans</i>		Veg.	YES	NO	LU	Jungermaniales	Scapaniaceae	SE	55.67585	13.35344	Nils Cronberg
287	BM64	<i>Fossombronina foveolata</i>		Spore	YES	YES	LU	Fossombroniales	Fossombroniaceae	SE	59.29698	13.29118	Nils Cronberg
266	BM59	<i>Frullania dilatata</i>		Spore	YES	YES	LU	Porellales	Frullaniaceae	SE	56.024212	13.127322	Nils Cronberg
304	BM65	<i>Frullania dilatata</i>		Veg.	YES	YES	LU	Porellales	Frullaniaceae	IT	46.22589	11.11708	Nils Cronberg
336	BM74	<i>Frullania dilatata</i>		Veg.	YES	YES	LU	Porellales	Frullaniaceae	SE	56.33629	12.88789	Nils Cronberg
264	new	<i>Frullania fragilifolia</i>		Veg.	NO	NO	LU	Porellales	Frullaniaceae	SE	56.02427	13.12746	Nils Cronberg
356	BM81	<i>Frullania tamarisci</i>		Veg.	YES	YES	LU	Porellales	Frullaniaceae	SE	56.02495	13.12299	Nils Cronberg
283	BM63	<i>Gymnocolea inflata</i>		Spore	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Anastrophyllaceae	SE	6183758	1376490	Nils Cronberg
309	BM68	<i>Liochlaena lanceolata</i>	<i>Jungermannia leiantha</i>	Veg.	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Jungermanniaceae	SE	59.65721	14.00877	Nils Cronberg
331	BM73	<i>Mesoptychia badensis</i>	<i>Leiocolea badensis</i>	Veg.	YES	NO	LU	Jungermaniales	Jungermanniaceae	SE	55.52314	12.90025	Nils Cronberg
358	BM82	<i>Lophocolea heterophylla</i>	<i>Chiloscyphus profundus</i>	Spore	YES	NO	LU	Jungermaniales	Lophocoleaceae	NO	63.359662	10.1362020	Fia Bengtsson
317	BM69	<i>Lophozia longidens</i>	<i>Lophozia longidens</i>	Veg.	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Lophoziaceae	SE	59.65721	14.00877	Nils Cronberg
295	new	<i>Lophozia silvicola</i>	<i>Lophozia ventricosa var. silvicola</i>	Veg.	NO	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Lophoziaceae	SE	57.97285	28.40077	Eliz Hayse

152	BM37	<i>Nardia sp</i>		Spore	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Gymnomitriaceae	IS	64.37287118	- 20.13756961	Isidora Loncarevic
339	BM76	<i>Marsupella sprucei</i>		Spore	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Gymnomitriaceae	SE	67.303931	16.679431	Anna Pielach
327	BM72	<i>Mylia anomala</i>		Veg.	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Myliaceae	SE	57.10323	14.57255	Nils Cronberg
323	BM70	<i>Nardia scalaris</i>		Veg.	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Gymnomitriaceae	SE	57.05699	14.43919	Nils Cronberg
247	BM53	<i>Nowellia curvifolia</i>		Spore	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Cephaloziaceae	SE	55.676419	13.353978	Nils Cronberg
265	BM58	<i>Nowellia curvifolia</i>		Spore	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Cephaloziaceae	SE	56.02427	13.12746	Nils Cronberg
371	BM87	<i>Odontoschisma sphagnii</i>		Veg.	YES	NO	LU	Jungermaniales	Cephaloziaceae	SE	57.11101	14.43389	Nils Cronberg
223	BM51	<i>Pellia cf borealis</i>	<i>P. epiphylla ssp. borealis</i>	Spore	YES	YES	LU	Pelliales	Pelliaceae	SE	55.67570	13.35354	Nils Cronberg
271	BM61	<i>Plagiochila asplenioides</i>		Veg.	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Plagiochilaceae	SE	56.025539	13.11828	Nils Cronberg
270	BM60	<i>Plagiochila porelloides</i>	<i>P. asplenioides subsp. porelloides</i>	Veg.	YES	YES	LU	Jungermaniales	Plagiochilaceae	SE	56.025539	13.11828	Nils Cronberg
372	BM88	<i>Ptilidium ciliare</i>		Veg.	YES	NO	LU	Ptilidiales	Ptilidiaceae	SE	57.11247	14.54081	Nils Cronberg
137	BM33	<i>Radula complanata</i>		Spore	YES	YES	LU	Porellales	Radulaceae	SE	56.024094	13.128104	Nils Cronberg
315	new	<i>Radula complanata</i>		Spore	NO	YES	LU	Porellales	Radulaceae	IT	46.22589	11.11708	Nils Cronberg
244	BM52	<i>Riccardia latifrons</i>		Spore	YES	YES	LU	Metzgeriales	Aneuraceae	SE	55.71373	13.20702	Nils Cronberg
373	BM89	<i>Riccia fluitans</i>		Veg.	YES	NO	LU	Marchantiales	Ricciaceae	SE	55.71373	13.20702	Nils Cronberg
308	BM67	<i>Scapania irrigua</i>		Veg.	YES	YES	LU	Jungermanniales	Scapaniaceae	SE	59.29698	13.29118	Nils Cronberg
352	BM79	<i>Scapania nemorea</i>		Spore	YES	YES	LU	Jungermanniales	Scapaniaceae	SE	56.02495	13.12299	Nils Cronberg
262	BM57	<i>Trichocolea tomentella</i>		Veg.	YES	YES	LU	Jungermanniales	Trichocoleaceae	SE	56.02395	13.130049	Nils Cronberg
305	BM66	<i>Trichocolea tomentella</i>		Veg.	YES	YES	LU	Jungermanniales	Trichocoleaceae	SE	59.65721	14.00877	Nils Cronberg
294	BM90	<i>Trilophozia quinquedentata</i>	<i>Tritomaria q.</i>	Veg.	YES	YES	LU	Jungermanniales	Lophoziaceae	SE	57.97285	28.40077	Eliz Hayse
394	new	<i>Clevea hyalina</i>		Veg.	NO	NO	LU	Marchantiales	Cleveaceae	SE	56.57410	16.47653	Nils Cronberg
401	new	<i>Frullania teneriffae</i>		Veg.	NO	NO	LU	Porellales	Frullaniaceae	FO	62.1370	-7.0157	Líggjas á Váli Smith
402	new	<i>Pellia cf neesiana</i>		Veg.	NO	NO	LU	Pelliales	pelliaceae	FO	62.1370	-7.0157	Líggjas á Váli Smith
393	new	<i>Porella cordaeana</i>		Veg.	NO	NO	LU	Porellales	Porellaceae	SE	55.69913	13.62099	Nils Cronberg

396	new	<i>Riccia sorocarpa</i>		Veg.	NO	NO	LU	Marchantiales	Ricciaceae	SE	56.57410	16.47653	Nils Cronberg
392	new	<i>Saccogyna viticulosus</i>		Veg.	NO	NO	LU	Jungermanniales	Saccogynaceae	FO	62.1275	-7.0211	Líggjas á Váli Smith